

NAVIGATING THE DIGITAL LANDSCAPE: EXPLORING CYBER LAW, INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY, AI, E-COMMERCE, AND E-GOVERNMENT

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ABSTRACT

In this legal scientific podcast article, Professor Thomas Hoeren provides valuable insights into the complex world of digital law. He delves into key aspects such as Cyber Law, Intellectual Property, AI (Artificial Intelligence), E-Commerce, and E-Government. With a wealth of experience and expertise, Professor Hoeren sheds light on the legal challenges and opportunities in this rapidly evolving digital landscape. Listeners will gain a deeper understanding of the legal implications surrounding technology and its impact on society, businesses, and governments.

Today for our next podcast I have invited the Professor of Information, Media, and Business Law at the University of Münster, Head of the Institute for Information, Telecommunication and Media Law Dr. Thomas Yohann Horen from Germany. Professor Thomas is a participant in the Central Asian Legal Research Fellowship program of Tashkent State University of Law.

Today, with Professor Thomas we are going to speak about Cyber Law and its Jurisdiction in the World. Cyber law, also known as internet law or information technology law, encompasses the legal issues related to the use of the internet, computers, and technology. Jurisdiction in the context of cyber law is a crucial aspect, as it determines which laws and regulations apply to online activities, and it can be quite complex in the global context. Today we can see digitalization in every sphere such as Cybercrime Jurisdiction, Data Privacy, e-commerce and contract law, e-government, Digital Intellectual Property, FinTech, Social Media law, digital rights, and so on. The need for cyber security is increasing day after day.

My first question dear Professor Thomas will be about cyber law. In what manner did cyber law evolve, creeping into our lives imperceptibly? How are matters of jurisdiction addressed within the realm of cyberspace?

My feeling is that most civilized countries have done their homework in the area of Internet law. So they have drafted beautiful legislation, and they have clear court decisions for their state territory. However, the system will not work in an international conflict because we still have the major problems of private international and international jurisdiction. So for instance, how can you enforce the US case in Russia or China? Because the Russian gods will not accept a US decision on the territory of Russia. That leaves a mosaic of strange gaps and interferences because the differences in national legislation are still astonishing. So I feel that the execution of national orders will become a real big threat for the future.

Today we can see the globalization of e-commerce and it is becoming an essential need in our lives. I want to ask you, what are the fundamental principles behind electronic commerce and electronic contracts, and what are the legal considerations involved? How can consumer rights be safeguarded in the realm of electronic commerce? What mechanisms are in place to address disputes stemming from e-commerce transactions?

I can only speak for Europe because your question is of course really broad. I can give a lecture for students in the last five hours but take Germany and the European Union. We have discovered that the general principles of contract law can be applied in the interest. So we have an offer and acceptance, we have a kind of consideration. The rules on errors and mistakes can be applied. So if somebody makes a mistake sending in the wrong error to another person the classical concept of error will be applicable. So that sounds good. However, the problem still remains for consumers. So we have indicated in Europe a whole framework of several direct directions and directives meaning that we have integrated a right to refuse them and cancel every internet contract within a certain period. That's very good. So the consumer can change his mind and say oh I made a very brilliant mistake. I want to cancel the contract. Another thing that we did in Europe was to integrate the idea of transparency. So the seller should be very clear on the internet about what he wants to offer. He should say real price. The real prohibit misleading advertisement and that's very important. But again as I said in the other question the problem still exists that we have a certain strange seller sitting in Ukraine or Uruguay and he is having really really nasty goods and products. So how can you enforce the rights of consumers in that international transaction? That seems to be very very complicated and that remains one of the biggest targets we have in Europe. Other problems are of course problems with banks. How can you pay on the Internet? It's complicated because how can you give your money and transact your money via via Internet? So you use a credit card which is risky. Can you transfer blockchain money? I mean it needs to have a lot of problems with blockchain money and cyber money. So there are still a lot of tasks to do. Other problems I can tell you are they are existing in other industries. We have one big problem with medical treatment. Okay now that a doctor gives you advice, consult, a client, a perceived person via the internet. It seems to be a very modern approach but how can you guarantee that the message of the doctor is transmitted in the correct way? So there is no misunderstanding of the doctor's opinion. That remains a problem and to a certain degree is still prohibited in Germany.

That's interesting, thank you, professor. Intellectual property has a status like traditional properties and we have to protect them from unlawful privatization. How is intellectual property protected in the cyber environment? Please, tell us about Issues of copyright infringement in the cyber environment.

That's interesting professor. Thank you for your answer my next question will be about intellectual property which has a touch like traditional properties and we have to protect them from unlawful presentation and how intellectual property is protected in the cyber environment please tell us the issues of copyright infringement in the cyber environment. Well, we had a lot of problems 10 years ago because a lot of especially young people use the internet for copying and sending illegal copies to their friends and companies build up illegal services to give access to illegal music and film files. To be had to be reduced and that has been done by inventing heavy assumptions. If you get caught if you get trapped with illegal copies you get a high punishment in Germany and other European states. So that is to decrease illegal copying. Young people are using YouTube or Spotify as well is no need to make illegal copies. And another idea which I like very much is the idea of using the technical chances on the internet for protecting using and files. So we call it digital rights management. So you take digital content and you build up a kind of anti-copying device so that is not technically possible to make illegal copies and that's another important trend we face in intellectual property. Blocking from screenshots and screen recordings. Exactly and that's a future and is highly done in Europe by big companies and music companies. So young people are not interested anymore in making illegal copies. Thank you and one additional question regarding digital intellectual property objects have you encountered disputes related to digital trademarks and domain names during your professional experience? Well, I have worked as a court of a peer judge for 15 years. So I've seen a lot of cases especially cases on digital rights management tools because the music industry and film industry sometimes put two restrictive measures on the digital content. It stops the whole access to digital content so even a legal user cannot use it their content. And that's the reason why we set in court. Digital content can be protected by technical tools and can be blocked and so on but only insofar as it is necessary for protecting copyright. So you cannot make two or harsh restrictions technical restrictions on certain digital content. And that has been decided by my court several times. It appears later on decided by the Supreme Court and we have even a famous decision of the European Court of Justice the same famous Nintendo case where the court has said exactly the same. Don't make two harsh restrictions from a technical point of allowed.

And one additional question regarding intellectual property objects, have you encountered disputes related to digital trademarks and domain names during your professional experience? What about trademarks in the digital environment and domain name disputes?

Having said how it's going in European countries. So tell you another story. I've not only worked as a court of appeal judge but I have been an arbitrator in the WIPO and the European arbitration court in the area of domain name disputes. I'm a total fan of arbitration. I think that is really working because you can imagine if you are disputing a domain name case in front of courts you need to wait for a long time it takes for sometimes six, or seven years and you have to wait for the decision of a court. So we need a more flexible and quicker tool than this arbitration and it is done by the WIPO as well as the European Court my feeling is that it's especially important for protecting against these domain name hijackers which are situated in China especially in China because we still have strange guys in China who reserve a domain with a trademark in it and say ah sorry I have made a resolution for your trademark as part of a domain but I can give you the domain if you pay me \$10,000 and then you can sue in front of

an arbitration court you only have to pay \$500, \$600, \$700 in within two weeks, three weeks you have your domain which you want so that's very easy and very sufficient. So it's a way to get domain names from China? Yeah especially from China because as I said in the beginning we have the problem of international jurisdiction. If somebody is coming from China how can you sue in China to enforce a trademark against the domain? It's very complicated and very expensive, you don't have any idea what's happening in China so you need another tool, another solution.

Thank you for sharing your experience as a judge and as an arbitrator. And next, my question will be about social media and its legal protection. How is social media legally regulated within the framework of cyber law, and what are the legal considerations regarding internet advertising and marketing in this context?

Well, we have a twofold system of protection within social media. We have on the one hand the idea of anti-competition law and applies for instance Germany to influencers. I don't like influencers, they are very nasty and if they are too harsh that means they are pushing their opinion too harshly beyond the internet we can protect against influencing and the court has done it. Influencers should be clear in saying we got money from the company so it has to be transparent in the system that we all know who is paying an influencer. So that's anti-competition law in Germany is 100 years old and it's very very easily enforced by courts.

The main problem I see is another one there is the power of social media platforms. There is now in Brussels a really big topic to use antitrust law or competition law and to build up new liability systems for fighting against Apple, Facebook, and others because in social media you can write everything that you want and lawyers always fear for instance of hate speech, nasty remarks which some crazy types write in social media like Facebook and saying my neighbor is the son of bad women and here is really annoying other people and frightening them. We need a kind of protection against the power of powerful platforms like meta and zeros and that will be done by European regulations because the EU acts as digital services, digital media acts that are brand-new, long, statutory tools to fight against meta and zeros. So you have special laws and codes on media law. We have special codes for media law and we have even more special codes for social media because the European Commission fears that big players in the area are Apple, Amazon, Meta, and Google and need to correct these big players in Europe not only to apply unfair competition laws on a national level but they have separate relations for these big social media players like meta and the others. The European Commission just made four important acts on regulating social media platforms like the digital media act which controls abusive powers and antitrust law. The European antitrust law was fought against Apple and the others. They have the Digital Services Act which regulates the liability of Meta and the others on a European level and even integrates a system of balancing the rights of users of this platform versus the rights of people writing on the platform. So there are very good regulations that need to be implemented on the national level because the codes and the national regulators need to be aware of what is happening in Brussels. So a lot of things to do in Europe.

So interesting, thank you. And today like traditional crimes we meet cybercrimes everywhere. Are cybercrimes on the internet similar to traditional crimes, and in what ways do they differ? What characterizes traditional cybercrime? What are the latest developments in the

field of cybercrime? How do cyber attacks manifest in the digital landscape? Is there a process for reporting incidents of cyber-fraud and identity theft?

Well, that is a twofold question. We have made in Europe a system that leads to a new cybercrime system so we have made new regulations for the protection against cybercrime cumulation we changed the cumulation so that Europe for a better fight against cybercrime and that has been made good but we had a problem again with the international jurisdiction who is in gets information if Russian or cyber Chinese tries to integrate into a system in Europe so we made a new system for building up a European agency who gets the all the information and how the information is going on till the final system operator gets really is the effective information knows what to do. There's a whole structure for protecting European businesses against cybercrime because the biggest threat at the moment is international cyber security we have very bad systems in Germany most companies are not very well equipped for the fight against hackers so that means the situation for instance at my university here and the neighbor university got hacked by hackers from China so we need to have a good system for getting quick information on threats and getting a high punishment of these hackers.

Thank you, professor. And your opinion regarding digitalization is very important and interesting for us. Could you share please, your prognoses for Prospects of cyber law? What are the benefits and dangers of artificial intelligence for humanity? How is artificial intelligence regulated? Are there national or international documents for using artificial intelligence?

I'm very proud to say that Europe is now developing the first regulation on AI law in the world so that's the first time Europe is quicker than the United States. The European Commissioner said we need to have a new regulation on that matter and that led to a new system of classification of each AI system. So each AI system has to be classified if it's a high-risk system if it's a middle-risk system or if is there no risk system if it's a high-risk system some systems are totally prohibited for instance social scoring made by AI is a big threat. As well as forbidden control of the eye of the eye for transportation that's all prohibited. In the middle section, Chat-GPT is classified as middle risk and you have to make a very transparent system as to where I have to be to explain everything that is integrated into the AI system so that a normal person can understand what is going on with for instance Chat-GPT.

So if you have no risk you're free to do what you want so as well as a kind of system for funding startup companies we want to build up a new AI system. That's what I like but it's still in discussion at the European Parliament level so in the next months we might have the first worldwide AI regulation and I would be proud to tell you more.

After enactment all this law I think we will describe that. Next year in September I will be with you and I hope to tell you more what was the final result. Now it's working in Germany on artificial intelligence regulation what is regulating and how it's serving people to protect their digital rights and humanity. Professor Thomas thank you enough for your engaging and informative presence on the podcast today your deep knowledge and eloquent explanations have truly eliminated the interactive world of cyber law and jurisdiction for our listeners I think your dedication to educating and empowering the next generation of legal professionals is commendable and we are fortunate to have had the opportunity to learn from you today your passion for this field is present and inspiring and as we conclude today's podcast we eagerly anticipate your return for future episodes as you give a promise next year in September we will

discuss with you the artificial intelligence law and your contributions are invaluable and we look forward to more south provoking discussions and insights.

Professor Thomas, we can't thank you enough for your engaging and informative presence on this podcast today. Your deep knowledge and eloquent explanations have truly illuminated the interactive world of cyber law and jurisdiction.

Your dedication to educating and empowering the next generation of legal professionals is commendable, and we are fortunate to have had the opportunity to learn from you. Your passion for this field is evident and inspiring.

As we conclude today's podcast, we eagerly anticipate your return for future episodes. Your contributions are invaluable, and we look forward to more thought-provoking discussions and insights.

Thank you, Professor Thomas, for your time, expertise, and the warmth you've brought to this conversation. We appreciate your dedication to the legal community and the broader knowledge-sharing space.

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